

Scientific activities on new media (Whatsapp) among Indian school and college students

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ABSTRACT

WhatsApp is one of the mediums of technology to be had together with I-smartphone, Android, home windows smartphone and whatsapp web in laptop which is famous many of the teenagers to send and collect spoken and written and text messages, audio and video calls, video, image to friends, and family. It is an powerful medium related the people for the go with the go with the flow of statistics and ideas. It's miles a tremendously addictive medium and the person's happiness and disappointment is based upon how he gets respond from the opposite users. Whatsapp makes the communication thru multimedia messaging. Any social network system popularity depends upon how well it meets consumer's personal need and preference. It enables the users to discover their possibilities and reviews.

NEW MEDIA LIKE WHATSAPP

The maximum exciting software program for MIM is whatsapp. The smart cellular phone is a tremendous tool for whatsapp platform. It allows the users to send and get keep of the facts, pictures, video, audio and textual content messages in actual time to people and group in free of fee. In international huge there are hundreds social networks and applications available to satisfy the person's personal need and desire. The social network systems designed a modern-day way of verbal exchange to make with pals, family and strangers to interact and discussion with them. Whatsapp is one of the maximum popular social media. It permits to preserve touch to anyone who are having whatsapp account in their smart phone. At a time, a textual content / voice message or vice clips or image may additionally moreover ship to a fixed consist 256 people. So, it can make the sector as clean with this contemporary communicate app.

ABOUT AND IMPORTANCE OF WHATSAPP

Whatsapp is a super medium for the youngsters for talking to friends, instructors and family members. It's far an effective medium to apprehend the attitude, interest, involvement of the customers.

CLINICAL AND SPORTS ACTIVITIES

The intellectual effects of whatsapp on users create more feelings of their life style. The users use whatsapp for retaining friendship family contributors, own family relations, and elegant fitness and for social, cultural and political information.

Brian motion and Jan Koum (2009) create whatsapp messages to make communication and distribution of multimedia messaging very easy and rapid. Andreas Kaplan (2011) discusses how WhatsApp's facilitates to percent and alternate data and thoughts among digital groups. The clients of whatsapp make bigger a advantageous intellectual mind-set in the course in their day today sports.

The take a look at shows that the whatsapp has created a sure sort of high-quality interplay many of the addicted companies that leads them to spend extra instances in whatsapp. The social and mental troubles positioned among the whatsapp customers are social isolation, missing of actual-lifestyles social dating, familial relationship, and multi-cultural environmental message sharing. Those are the end result of the excessive use of whatsapp which comes beneath more familiar form of technological dependency.

Bucker et al (2012) argues the individual that is arguable to pro-social relationship with one-of-a-kind character except they increase less outstanding, argumentative, uncooperative and merciless dating with other humans. The unpleasant individual uses internet through gratifying his bad dispositions. The examine indicates the most of the kids in Tamilnadu regularly checking the whatsapp messages and retaining contact with cellular facts which makes some mental behavioral samples like shyness, loneliness, stress and moody conduct a number of the WhatsApp customers.

SOCIOLOGICAL AND CULTURAL ACTIVITIES

Kim et al (2008) turn out to be privy to the nicely-adjusted whatsapp users not to seek social contacts at the internet. The folks who are having reviews within the fantastic emotions and network participation are make investments time in social courting and they will be not bear in mind cyber courting for their social guide. The majority of the young adults use whatsapp software program for speak me to buddies on one-of-a-kind issues in place of instructional traits. The scholars preferred to apply whatsapp once they experience uninteresting of classroom lectures. However, whatsapp is one of the excellent coaching and studying tool for the academics and novices. However, U.S. likes India it isn't always but used as a device for training and gaining knowledge of the subjects.

It's far a clean and rapid communicate tool for passing and sharing thoughts the diverse customers' network. Johanson Yeboah & George Dominic Ewur (2014) additionally shows whatsapp is not balancing the web sports and educational standard overall performance of the children. Seeing that whatsapp message is extra social, casual and conversational, it creates greater powerful of their day-by-day habitual lifestyles, own family life and their psychological behavioral sample in their lifestyles.

Whatsapp is extra handy and interactive for the powerful rework messages and mind the various young people who are disable to satisfy his pricey and nears in my view. Whatsapp is a primary reason for social isolation which used for selling the virtual dating. These days whatsapp lets in the youngsters for having steady touch with friends and own family and also to fulfill their desires of information, entertainment, and education.

STATISTICS SERIES FOR THIS RESEARCH

The records for the have a study is accumulated, based on the method of judgmental sampling method. There are 200 whatsapp customers in particular classes decided on from Tamilnadu for the test. Within the survey method, the random sampling technique is used for collecting the facts the diverse children among the age organization 15 and 24. The collection

of statistics primarily based on various social hierarchal, financial and cultural historical past of the users completely one hundred guys and a hundred girls.

Figure- 1: The data selection for this study

Percentage of sharing of text, video, etc and chatting and taking of their experience

The result of the study reveals 80% of the users using whatsapp for sharing the text, audio, video and pictures. Remaining 20% youth use whatsapp for chatting, talking and for sharing their experiences.

Table: percentage of sharing of text, video, etc and chatting and taking of their experience

Sl.No.	Types of user of Whatsapp	Total nos. of user	Percentage
1.	Sharing the text, audio, video and pictures	160	80%
2.	Chatting, talking and sharing their experiences	40	20%

Out of 80% (160 persons out of 200 persons)

The study shows in among with the 80% of sharing of messages 40% users use whatsapp for sharing the social, cultural and economic originated information, 18% for video and pictures sharing, 9% for entertainment, and 8% for general information and 5% for sharing the profile of other whatsapp.

Figure- 2: Out of 80% (160 persons out of 200 persons)

Out of 20% (40 persons out of 200 persons)

In the remaining 20%, users use whatsapp for chatting 13%, talking 4%, and 3% for sharing their experiences. The survey reveals 79% of the users use whatsapp for chatting with their friends and only 21% chatting with other friends.

Figure- 3: Out of 20% (40 persons out of 200 persons)

The study shows the most of the youth in Tamilnadu regularly checking the whatsapp messages and keeping in touch with mobile data which makes them in some psychological behavioral patterns like shyness, loneliness, stress and moody behavior among the users.

RESULT OF THE STUDY

In the survey, the user pointed out the various uses of whatsapp in their life style activities:

- Whatsapp helps them to establish friendship
- It helps to provide information about job opportunities
- It helps to share knowledge among the person who are having accounts in the whatsapp group
- It helps to get more informative database
- It helps to build social relationship across boundaries
- It uses as communication media for sharing personal experiences, pictures and video
- It serves as common platform for some social incidences across the country
- It uses to connect with dear ones
- It helps youth for connecting the experts, for gaining and for sharing knowledge among themselves.

CONCLUSION

Whatsapp works with internet connectivity and helps its users create groups and send unlimited images, video and audio messages. The youth lose natural learning capacities due to the habits of depending upon the internet. The user uses whatsapp for sharing audio files, video files, and documents and for updating status. The most negative aspects of whatsapp is that it distracts the youth from concentrating the routine work and consuming more time of them.

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